

DARE UK

DARE UK Sprint Exemplar Full Report: Governance Recommendations for Non-Traditional Researchers in Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

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1. Executive Summary

Putting data at the centre of responses to challenges in systems (e.g. health and care or economic) is critical to improving services. Developments in technology such as AI and partnerships between the NHS and private- or third-sector organisations can result in new and improved healthcare technologies, treatments and medical devices that support better outcomes for patients. Reaping the benefits from the wealth of routinely collected data in the public sector to support frontline services requires research, development, and innovation resource such as software/AI developers and expertise from across sectors.

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) provide secure and trusted infrastructures and services to create an efficient and safe approach to store, link and enable access to data. However, data access to support AI, software development or researchers outside academia or clinical settings has been limited and remains largely aspirational due to a perceived lack of public trust, and changes required in legal, technological and governance structures.

To respond to this challenge, DataLoch and the electronic Data Research and Innovation Service (eDRIS) embarked on this Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK) sprint to design a governance framework supporting safe data use for researchers developing novel technologies or from outside academia (from this point on referred to as non-traditional researchers). This activity included a quantitative and qualitative public engagement process of survey and workshops to examine public requirements to allow these types of data uses, and creating a researcher training module specifically for these types of researchers to supplement current national training offerings. Based on this work and engagement within the TRE community, DataLoch has a governance framework in place that is currently being tested for health and social care data in Scotland.

This report provides a brief description of the challenges for TREs to support non-traditional researcher access, and recommendations for governance structures, with supporting evidence from public and TRE engagement, alongside a case study example of one Scottish TRE's implementation. While this report focuses on the use of health data and is based in Scotland due to the contributing TREs, the recommendations are likely to be applicable across secure data use in the UK – including the NHS (England) plans for Secure Data Environments.

1.1. Summary of Recommendations

Recommendations in this report consider aspects required for each of the Five Safes¹ framework *beyond* those already in place for traditional researchers. They have been designed to be easily adapted from current processes and incorporated, where appropriate, for both traditional and non-traditional TRE projects. They also align with the recently published Scottish Government draft principles for data sharing².

1. Safe Projects

- 1.1 Any use of personal data must have an explicit aim to deliver public value. In addition to benefit to the public, researchers must describe benefit of the work to their own organisation and the data provider.

¹ Desai, Tanvi; Ritchie, Felix; Welpton, Richard (2016). "Five Safes: designing data access for research". Bristol Business School Working Papers in Economics

² <https://blogs.gov.scot/digital/2022/08/19/draft-principles-for-unlocking-the-value-of-scotlands-public-sector-personal-data-for-public-benefit/>

1.2 All projects should complete an acceptable form of ethical review – reviewing panels should include AI data ethics expertise where required.

2. Safe People

2.1 Research projects must have a named organisation taking responsibility for the design and conduct of the activity.

2.2 Researcher organisations:

- Must sign an organisational agreement with the data provider on data use;
- Must be assessed for suitability of data access/use to demonstrate trustworthiness; and
- Should consider partnering with an academic or NHS institution.

2.3 Researchers must:

- Demonstrate relevant expertise and ability to support the project/data use;
- Complete supplementary training modules with specific content targeted at those using secure data without an academic research background
- Sign a user access agreement, countersigned by a senior member of their organisation.

2.4 National organisations supporting TREs should consider maintaining a national unsafe user/organisation list on behalf of TREs.

3. Safe Settings

3.1 TREs should develop services to:

- Increase approved software libraries;
- Allow virtual machines with varying configurations of hardware access and temporary internet access;
- Security risk assess new software and allow installation separately to data access;
- Support delegated software installation; and
- Isolate non-traditional researcher project spaces/virtual machines.

3.2 TRE access should be restricted to organisationally managed machines and organisationally managed IP addresses only.

4. Safe Data

4.1 Data providers should document any restrictions/caveats on use or users.

4.2 TRE staff should receive training in AI/ML techniques to understand data requirements and contributions to results, supplemented by expertise within review panels.

4.3 Disclosure risks (inbound and exbound) for novel/other types of data (e.g. qualitative, image, genomic) need to be identified and mitigated by TREs, data providers and researchers.

5. Safe Outputs

5.1 Risk assessment and mitigation of outputs from novel analysis techniques, tools, software and data need to be identified and understood by TRE staff and researchers. Safe output criteria should be developed between TREs for consistency.

5.2 Any TRE-specific disclosure control policies and requirements should be made clear to researchers on provision of data access.

5.3 Projects should be followed up to determine how project results were used and benefits realised.

6. Overall

6.1 TRE governance documentation such as risk assessments should be amended to include specifics in relation to non-traditional researcher data access.

2. Purpose

This recommendation paper is one of the main outputs of a Sprint project to develop a governance model and training module to support non-traditional researchers to use sensitive health data within TREs.

The project has been led by the DataLoch team at the University of Edinburgh, in collaboration with Public Health Scotland’s (PHS) Electronic Data Research and Innovation Service (eDRIS). DataLoch is a data service that curates health and social care data for 1.6m people in South-East Scotland. Approved applicants receive de-identified data extracts via the National Safe Haven – a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) managed by eDRIS.

DataLoch and eDRIS have considered each aspect of the Five Safes³ framework, in conjunction with public and TRE/governance staff perspectives, to develop recommendations on the controls required. This report provides a description of the challenges these types of researchers bring to TREs, recommendations that TREs can adopt, along with a case study of how DataLoch has implemented them.

³ Desai, Tanvi; Ritchie, Felix; Welpton, Richard (2016). "Five Safes: designing data access for research". Bristol Business School Working Papers in Economics

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3. Project Team

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Atul Anand, DataLoch Clinical Lead, NHS Lothian: Atul is an NHS Consultant Geriatrician and Senior Clinical Research Fellow at the University of Edinburgh. His role within DataLoch and in this project has been working with the technical team and clinical colleagues to bring a clinical perspective to the design. ORCID: 0000-0002-6428-4554

Kathy Harrison, DataLoch Programme Lead, University of Edinburgh: Kathy is a project management professional responsible for launching the DataLoch data service, including the service's robust, innovative, and agile governance process. She is the overall project manager for this project.

Amy Tilbrook, Data Ethics Professional and DataLoch Information Governance, University of Edinburgh: Amy is an accredited ethics professional, with extensive experience of health data research governance. She has been responsible for leading the governance definition work package. ORCID: 0000-0002-0294-2101

Stuart Dunbar, PPIE lead, University of Edinburgh: Stuart has a PhD in science engagement and has been responsible for engaging with the public to understand perspectives on non-traditional researcher access to data. These perspectives have been key to the recommendations on governance conditions.

Carole Morris, eDRIS Head of Service, Public Health Scotland (PHS): The PHS eDRIS team have run the National Safe Haven for many years, supporting the administration of hundreds of research projects. Carole has been responsible within this project for consulting on the national requirements from the TRE prototype. ORCID: 0000-0001-8150-8217

Michelle Evans, Talent Programme Director, University of Edinburgh: Michelle is the Talent Lead for the DDI Health and Social Care programme at the Usher Institute and Director of the online MSc in Data Science for Health and Social Care, responsible for the shaping the future of a major new health & social care programme for Edinburgh & South East Scotland as part of the DDI initiative at the University of Edinburgh. Michelle has been responsible for leading the work package to develop training content and make it available on a public learning platform. ORCID: 0000-0001-7014-6695

Talent team members: Chris, Richard: Responsible for designing the training module, and developing the module delivery and technical solution.

4. Background

Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) and other national bodies aim to increase the access and use of health data in a trustworthy and ethical way in order to develop improvements in the UK's health technology and deliver benefits to patients and the population.

Putting data at the centre of responses to challenges in systems (e.g., health and care or economic) is critical to improving services through research, innovation, and planning. The population-wide insights over a significant time-scale that are possible through the safe use of routinely collected data are an efficient use of resources, and can speed up the process of introducing new innovations into frontline services.

Developments in technology – such as AI and partnerships between the NHS and private- or third-sector organisations – can result in new and improved healthcare technologies, treatments and medical devices that support better outcomes for patients. Reaping the benefits from the wealth of routinely collected data in the public sector to support frontline services requires research, development, and innovation resource such as software/AI developers and expertise from across sectors.

As recognised in several recent national reviews^{4,5,6} and the public (see below), data providers such as the NHS cannot survive without innovative uses of data, which can only be provided by embracing new and emerging technologies such as AI development, or supporting research from beyond the academic and clinical sector.

From the public engagement workstream

Survey: Views on data sharing with AI developers were broadly positive, with a majority (70%) in support of AI developers using health data about them for research and development purposes. Only 14% opposed this position.

Workshops:

"I think saying the term 'Artificial intelligence' makes me go, 'Oh, that's weird,' just because it's so new and it's like stepping into the unknown in terms of medicine. But there's so much scope to do so much good, so I don't think it would stop me supporting this."

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) provide secure and trusted infrastructures and services to create an efficient and safe approach to store, link and enable access to data, as the data required for such research is typically detailed, personal and may be sensitive and therefore must be treated with proportionate care and governance. TREs support privacy by design and the majority support academic researchers and practitioners/clinicians within subject specific domains (e.g., health, economics), utilising frameworks like the Five Safes as tools to support the safe use of data.

⁴ <https://www.HDRUK.ac.uk/case-studies/boosting-health-innovation-through-industry-partnerships/>

⁵ Kavianpour et al. A Review of Trusted Research Environments to Support Next Generation Capabilities based on Interview Analysis Preprint: <https://s3.ca-central-1.amazonaws.com/assets.jmir.org/assets/preprints/preprint-33720-accepted.pdf>

⁶ E.g. the Goldacre Review: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1067053/goldacre-review-using-health-data-for-research-and-analysis.pdf

The Five Safes framework

The Five Safes framework is a set of principles adopted by a range of data centres providing secure access to data around the world. Assessing each aspect of the framework individually and as a whole is part of how TREs ensure data are hosted and accessed safely. The Five Safes as adopted by TREs are:

- Safe Projects – Projects are assessed by governance panels, so data are only used for valuable, ethical research that delivers clear public benefit.
- Safe People – Researchers are trained in safe handling of data and sign agreements covering their responsibilities when accessing data.
- Safe Settings – Access to data is via secure, restricted technology systems, there is no access to the internet or copy/paste functionality, information going in or out is checked by TRE staff.
- Safe Data – Researchers use data that have been de-identified and extracts comprise the minimum amount of data to fulfil the purpose of their project and
- Safe Outputs – All outputs such as tables, graphs, trends are checked to ensure they cannot indirectly identify people.

As part of the Five Safes, any person wishing to access data within a TRE must follow an approved application process and meet key governance criteria to ensure their purposes are legitimate and in the public interest – these criteria have been designed for researchers from academic/clinical backgrounds completing quantitative statistical analysis (“traditional researchers”) which have produced great insights and development across domains. Safe data access to support AI, software development or from researchers outside of these domains to date has been limited and remains largely aspirational due to a perceived lack of public trust and changes required in legal, technological and governance structures to support the requirements of these researchers – TREs must change if they are to support next generation researchers and make best use of data.

This report provides recommendations for TRE governance structures to support non-traditional researcher access, with supporting evidence from public and TRE engagement, and a case study example of one TRE’s implementation. The authors work within TREs primarily using health and social care data therefore have focused on this domain, but consider the recommendations applicable to all secure data use.

The report is expected to be useful to TREs considering or allowing non-traditional researcher data access, and therefore are already familiar with concepts such as the Five Safes framework⁷. These recommendations outline requirements on top of current governance and processes used within TREs for traditional academic research use – most are also applicable and will augment traditional research use and so should be applied across all projects. The issues identified in this paper, associated recommendations and DataLoch’s framework were developed through:

⁷ Desai, Tanvi; Ritchie, Felix; Welpton, Richard (2016). "Five Safes: designing data access for research". Bristol Business School Working Papers in Economics

- Desk research including evaluating and adapting guidance from HDR UK⁸ and the University of Dundee⁹;
- A programme of public engagement with residents from South-East Scotland¹⁰;
- An issues workshop attended by TRE staff and governance panel chair;
- Iterative feedback from over 20 TRE and governance experts within Scotland and England, including other DARE UK sprints;
- Extensive engagement with safe haven providers at the University of Edinburgh, current traditional researchers, and prospective users of the service.

DataLoch has been presented as an initial case study for implementation of the recommendations in a TRE. Feedback on the feasibility of implementation in other TREs or utilising different data is welcomed.

Alongside these recommendations, a researcher training module has been developed that can be incorporated into the Safe People aspect of any governance model. This training module is designed to equip non-traditional users with the skills, understanding and credibility to access health and social care data in TREs and is intended as a supplement to existing training modules that have been designed for academic researchers.

5. Scope and Assumptions

This work and recommendations investigated what controls may need to be in place to allow non-traditional researchers to access data within a TRE. When using the term researcher within this document, this means any person applying to access data within a TRE to complete a defined piece of work looking to answer a question, develop a tool or further knowledge in relation to benefiting public health (“project”).

Traditional researchers in this context are defined as researchers from academic organisations or NHS clinicians doing quantitative, statistical research using standard statistical software.

Non-Traditional researchers may be:

- AI tool developers – whether in a traditional research organisation (e.g. University) or elsewhere.
- Third-sector/commercial organisation researchers – completing conventional (descriptive and inferential) statistical research, software development or AI model development.

There are a number of assumptions that these recommendations are working under:

- TREs run a UK-based service with individual-level personal data on UK citizens – including special category data (such as health data) as defined under UK GDPR¹¹.
- TREs are already familiar with Five Safes framework¹² –the recommendations contained herein are to be applied in addition/as adaptations to existing controls and can apply to all projects.

⁸ HDR UK Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems
<https://zenodo.org/record/5767586#.Yr2Dm3bMKUk>

⁹ Kavianpour et al. A Review of Trusted Research Environments to Support Next Generation Capabilities based on Interview Analysis Preprint: <https://s3.ca-central-1.amazonaws.com/assets.jmir.org/assets/preprints/preprint-33720-accepted.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf>

¹¹ [Guide to the UK General Data Protection Regulation \(UK GDPR\) | ICO](#)

¹² Desai, Tanvi; Ritchie, Felix; Welpton, Richard (2016). "Five Safes: designing data access for research". Bristol Business School Working Papers in Economics

- TREs are following existing best practices for traditional researcher access, as per the HDR UK Principles and Best Practices for Trusted Research Environments paper¹³ – including good practice pseudonymisation of all data accessed within the TRE, project application review processes, researcher training, secure environments and checking of outputs by TRE staff.

The recent HDR UK Green Paper¹⁰ outlines extensions to the Five Safes model to include Safe Computing and Safe Return. However, as neither DataLoch nor eDRIS utilises either mechanism (commercial/cloud safe settings or consented data returned to individuals) this was considered out of scope.

The expected audiences of this report are all those who would be involved in supporting a TRE to implement non-traditional researcher access, including TRE managers, governance and ethics panels and national bodies such as UKRI and HDR UK involved in creating national guidance to support best research practice.

6. Challenges for non-traditional researcher data access

Challenges were identified through engagement with TRE infrastructure providers, a workshop with TRE and governance panel staff, and the public engagement workstream. These identified the most important things for TREs to overcome to support non-traditional researchers are:

- Non-traditional researchers may have the skills, resource, and innovation to drive forward improvements in health and social care, but do not necessarily have the background in research or safe data use that reassures the public and data providers that data will not be misused – maliciously or (more likely) inadvertently.
- Projects developing AI or other emerging technologies are often novel or exploratory, requiring large amounts of data, novel software and data types, and an agile risk assessment and ethics evaluation.
- Complex AI models require more information to describe and reproduce, increasing the possibility that sensitive personal data can be inferred from such descriptions.
- TRE and Information Governance staff, or their supporting legal teams, may not have understanding of the methodologies/technologies used in this novel research, or the risks concerned.
- There may be a lack of clarity across TREs around Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and commercialisation possibilities around both data accessed by organisations and outcomes of research (e.g., AI tools developed) that are used outside the TRE.
- New and smaller organisations may not be established enough to provide reassurance that:
 - Safe data practices are known and followed;
 - There is enough understanding of the contractual requirements in data sharing and access;
 - They have the ability to disseminate the results and provide the promised impact; and/or
 - They have longevity to make best use of the data.
- Large commercial organisations, especially international ones, have been considered as less trustworthy by the public to safely and appropriately use data¹⁴. Data providers and TREs rely on public trust to

¹³ HDR UK Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems

<https://zenodo.org/record/5767586#.Yr2Dm3bMKUk>

¹⁴ [https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-](https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/Public%20perspectives%20on%20the%20use%20of%20health%20data%20in%20research%20and%20innovation.pdf)

[06/Public%20perspectives%20on%20the%20use%20of%20health%20data%20in%20research%20and%20innovation.pdf](https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/Public%20perspectives%20on%20the%20use%20of%20health%20data%20in%20research%20and%20innovation.pdf)

function, and the repercussions of losing it are large. Perceptions collected over this work from both the public¹⁵ and TRE community are that such organisations may:

- prioritise profit over public good; and
- be challenging to hold accountable for data misuse due to their legal resources.

From the public deliberation workshops

“In a research institute you’re going into it for a greater good, not because you want to be a millionaire. Its purpose, the people and the ethics behind it all tie up properly. That isn’t always the case with commercial companies.”

7. Recommendations

7.1. Safe Projects

All projects supported in TREs require assessment for their benefit to the public and whether the use of the data requested is appropriate. Data Providers/TRE Governance Review Panels assess whether the project satisfies criteria of being a “Safe Project”. Currently projects are often required to go through some form of ethical and peer review and are usually published on a data use register¹⁶.

To incorporate non-traditional researchers, the Safe Project criteria should also include:

6.1.1 Any use of personal data, not available in the public domain must have an explicit aim to deliver public value. In addition to benefit to the public, researchers should describe benefit of the work to their own organisation and the data provider.

Research use of personal data must have public benefit, and TREs and researchers must be transparent in data use by law. This recommendation supports the project reviewer in assessing whether the research is motivated primarily by profit, and how this research would benefit the NHS/data provider – both key concerns from the public in allowing non-traditional researchers access.

Although data-driven innovation can drive new insights, the direct public benefit of exploratory research into developing an AI tool for a commercial organisation can be difficult for researchers to describe and approvers to review – the chain of causation can seem long and convoluted. Outlining how the specific research will benefit both the data provider and the researcher’s own organisation gives a clearer picture of how the public benefit might be realised.

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if [researchers] can demonstrate a clear public benefit for their use of the data, a positive intended outcome, and a clear reason why they need the data.

¹⁵ <https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://www.hdruc.ac.uk/access-to-health-data/data-use-registers/#:~:text=Data%20use%20registers%20are%20a,patient%20data%20is%20being%20requested.>

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if researchers agree the data is not going to be used solely for profit.

Key Red Line: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers becomes unacceptable if researchers cannot demonstrate the potential benefits to the NHS from the research.

“Certain companies aren’t [motivated by] the greater good, they are out for their own good. But they have the money and power to be able to help the greater good. Those companies should have to go through the same safeguards as everybody else has to, and transparency is absolutely key to enable [those companies] to access data.”

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has incorporated questions in its application form to specify within a public benefit statement how the research project will benefit the NHS.

6.1.2 All projects should complete an acceptable form of ethical review – reviewing panels should include AI data ethics expertise where required.

The UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care requires an ethical favourable opinion for any health data use for the purposes of “research”. Research using health data is defined as *“the attempt to derive generalisable or transferable new knowledge to answer or refine relevant questions with scientifically sound methods.”*

This includes:

- non-interventional health and social care research;
- activities that are carried out in preparation for or as a consequence of the interventional part of the research;
- projects that aim to generate hypotheses; and
- methodological research and descriptive research

But excludes:

- audits of practice and service evaluations.

As acknowledged by the HRA in their work to streamline Data-Driven Research such as AI and data-driven technologies¹⁷, it is not always clear if a project using or developing AI falls within the above definition and requires ethical review – despite the growing evidence that ethical issues and challenges exist in this sort of work. As outlined in DataLoch’s public consultations in 2022, all projects from non-traditional researchers should be considered and reviewed by relevant experts – even when not fully falling within the category of research.

To support existing ethical reviewers in making proportionate decisions on risks of new technologies and methodology, panel membership should be expanded to include representation from AI and data ethics professionals to provide an informed view. This representation could involve training existing reviewers, inviting AI ethics experts to join, or the development of a pool of AI ethics experts that are called upon as required for individual projects.

¹⁷ [Streamlining Data-Driven Research \(SDDR\) - Health Research Authority \(hra.nhs.uk\)](https://www.hra.nhs.uk/streamlining-data-driven-research-sddr)

TREs will need to decide what an acceptable ethical review is within their area. It is possible that existing ethical review panels (e.g., NHS, University, National Statistician’s Data Ethics Advisory Committee - NSDEC) could be expanded to include project types not just falling under subject-specific research and have a streamlined process for those requiring a lower proportionate review (e.g., service management) – the NSDEC self-assessment¹⁸ checklist approach may be considered useful here. Third-sector and commercial organisations not partnering with an academic/NHS body should be signposted to NSDEC or another national ethics body that the TREs agree are appropriate.

From the public deliberation workshops

Survey: Having the project being reviewed by an ethics committee including an NHS professional was required by 2/3rds of respondents for both traditional and non-traditional access.

Workshop:

“...companies should have to go through the same safeguards as everybody else has to, and transparency is absolutely key to enable [those companies] to access data.”

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if research requests are subject to review and scrutiny by an ethics panel.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has integrated an ethical review process for all projects within its governance group and has incorporated AI data ethics expertise to be called upon as needed.

7.2. Safe People

In addition to processes and safeguards put in place by TREs themselves, the individuals allowed access to data must be trusted to handle it appropriately – and be able to demonstrate that trustworthiness. DataLoch’s public consultation in 2022 highlighted the concern the public feel about who has access to data and possible data breaches – specifically showing less trust for international and private sector organisations (which are likely to employ non-traditional researchers). Therefore, Safe People criteria requires an assessment of both the individual accessing data, and the organisation requesting the work. The considerations around allowing non-traditional researchers within this category are:

6.2.1 Research projects must have a named organisation taking responsibility for the design and conduct of the activity.

The UK policy framework for Health and Social Care sets out requirements for all health and social care research to have a “Sponsor”:

“The sponsor is the individual, organisation or partnership that takes on overall responsibility for proportionate, effective arrangements being in place to set up, run and report a research project. All health and social care research has a sponsor. The sponsor is normally expected to be the employer of the chief investigator in the case

¹⁸ <https://uksa.statisticsauthority.gov.uk/the-authority-board/committees/national-statisticians-advisory-committees-and-panels/national-statisticians-data-ethics-advisory-committee/ethics-self-assessment-tool/>

of non-commercial research or the funder in the case of commercial research. (The employer or funder is not automatically the sponsor; they explicitly accept the responsibilities of being the sponsor).¹⁹

While this requirement currently only extends to health research projects, the sponsorship framework provides clear accountability and supports better designed and completed projects – having a single organisation that takes responsibility for the legal, ethical and appropriate running of the research. This is recommended to extend beyond pure health research (as defined by HRA) to all projects taking place in TREs. In practice it's possible the TRE itself will manage several of the sponsorship responsibilities but TREs can decide whether they will accept this role.

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Red Line: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers becomes unacceptable if researchers are unable to demonstrate that they, or the organisation they are part of, have the track record, skills and expertise to research with health data.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch provides a delegated sponsorship review of some projects, however sponsorship responsibility for non-traditional researchers is expected to be with the employer of the lead researcher. As DataLoch and eDRIS deal primarily in projects utilising health data and therefore falling under the UK policy framework, we welcome feedback on whether this recommendation is feasible for data types other than health.

6.2.2 Researcher organisations:

Must sign an organisational agreement with the data provider on data use

This agreement outlines the responsibilities of the parties involved in the research, can cover several individual projects and should be signed by a relevant authority within the organisation (i.e., not the researcher). These agreements are likely already used for traditional researchers, but may need amendment to include non-traditional specifics such as e.g., intellectual property rights of models produced. These agreements could also include caveats on profits of the research going back into the NHS, or not being used to increase individual prices, but it is unclear at this stage how feasible this is.

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if researchers can only have access to the data that they request, and only for the purposes that they specify in their request for access.

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if research ultimately benefits the NHS (either through sharing of findings or outcomes from the research, or through financial contribution from any profit made).

Key Red Line: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers becomes unacceptable if there is any use of the data beyond its stated purpose (for instance using the data to target people).

¹⁹ <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/policies-standards-legislation/uk-policy-framework-health-social-care-research/uk-policy-framework-health-and-social-care-research/#sponsors>

Implementation within the DataLoch service

See [Risk Assessment and Contracts](#) section.

Must be assessed for suitability of data access/project use

Traditional researchers are employed by organisations with a defined key purpose of research – such as academic organisations or the NHS. The research purpose is often outlined in law²⁰ and as such organisations often have published codes of conduct (e.g., WHO code of conduct²¹), or published data handling standards for research as evidence of compliance.

Non-traditional researchers may not be employed by an organisation with such a clearly defined public benefit purpose, or with any industry standard of completing research/handling data. Therefore, TREs should assess whether the organisation's motivation includes public interest research (rather than purely profit) and that they can be trusted not to misuse data. DataLoch's public engagement work defines some principles that may guide TREs in their assessment of organisational suitability²².

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if researchers can conform to meeting and adhering to a quality standard, code of conduct or an agreed set of terms and conditions.

Key Red Line: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers becomes unacceptable if the organisation has a history of misuse of data or unethical practices.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch current considerations include (reviewed annually):

- Organisational role – Clinical/Contract Research Organisations/organisations that work mainly with selling information or services are unlikely to be accepted.
- Organisational experience – either in similar projects/collaborations/research, or sensitive data access to e.g., health, finance, insurance, consumer data. Evidence of conforming to code of practice/standards of research or any previous misuse of data (e.g., notification to ICO).
- Organisational values – these should align to data provider/TRE.
- Financial due diligence assessment – historical and projected financial position of the organisation, using industry standard tools.
- Headquarters location of organisation – non-UK organisations may have different data protection risks to consider.
- Benefit to the data provider/region – organisations with opportunities to benefit NHS or the local area are preferred.
- Organisational openness – assessment of transparency of organisation, willingness to collaborate and share expertise.

²⁰ E.g., Universities (Scotland) Act 1966/UK Higher Education and Research Act 2017/National Health Service Act 2006

²¹ <https://www.who.int/about/ethics/code-of-conduct-for-responsible-research>

²² [https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-](https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf)

[07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf](https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf)

Should consider partnering with an academic or NHS institution

HDR UK requires researchers within the HDR UK Alliance to “have a formal relationship with a bona fide research organisation that requires compliance with appropriate research governance and management systems”. This could be fulfilled by TREs requiring organisations partner with an academic or NHS institution to bring oversight and foster well-designed research. Academic/NHS institutions could take on the “sponsor” or oversight role to lend assurance that research was well-run. Advantages of partnering and bringing academic/NHS individuals on project teams include:

- increased trust from the public;
- provide legal support for smaller organisations that have not dealt with data sharing laws before;
- taking some responsibility off TREs for providing some accountability and continuity should the organisation for any reason change legal status by the end of the project (organisational takeovers, bankruptcy, etc); and
- reduce the risks of prolonged legal battles in the event of a serious breach.

However, bona fide research organisations are not limited to academic/NHS institutions and enforcing this as a requirement may:

- restrict innovation – if organisations are not able to secure a partnership due to e.g. lack of contacts; or
- put pressure on already stretched resources in traditional organisations (e.g. research and legal team) by increasing the number of projects to administer.

Note that any TREs/researchers sharing data under the Digital Economy Act (DEA 2017) may feel the requirement under the DEA for researchers to comply with the UK Statistics Authority Code of Practice²³ should fulfil this recommendation – however DataLoch does not share under this provision and so has not investigated it.

From the public engagement workstream

Key Red Line: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers becomes unacceptable if the researchers are unable to demonstrate that they, or the organisation they are part of, have the track record, skills, and expertise to research with health data.

“The words ‘academic or health care professional’ give me comfort.”

Survey Finding: Respondents were informed that most pharmaceutical company research studies with NHS patients involve a partnership with the NHS and were asked whether that made them feel more confident about research funded by pharmaceutical companies, less confident, or made no difference. Over two in five (46%) said it made them feel more confident and 45% said it made no difference, while 6% said it made them feel less confident about these studies.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch recommends organisations consider such partnerships, and encourages project teams to include academics or clinicians to enhance data understanding, but does not restrict access to only teams with this relationship.

²³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/digital-economy-act-2017-part-5-codes-of-practice/research-code-of-practice-and-accreditation-criteria>

6.2.3 Researchers must:

Demonstrate relevant expertise to support the project/data use

Researchers skilled in AI development, or from outside the sector providing the data, may lack fundamental knowledge of the datasets themselves that could affect the work – e.g. how it is collected and pre-processed. Given the complexity of datasets usually available within TREs, this can seriously hamper the effectiveness of the project proposal, timescales, impact of results and reputation of data providers and TREs²⁴. The demonstration of expertise or track record within the project team was deemed vital by the public engagement work²⁵ but does not necessarily need to be a formal qualification, but rather an indication of, for example, a track record of using this type of data and/or in this sector, or having an academic or data provider representative on the research team.

From the public deliberation workshops

“We would feel more reassured if the organisation was partnering with the NHS or with a university, and therefore subject to their relevant codes of practice.”

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch application form includes a field for details on relevant expertise of the applicant(s)/research team and how it applies to the fields(s) to be researched.

Complete supplementary training modules with specific content targeted at those using secure data without an academic research background

There are several approved training courses for using TREs in the UK. The most common are the MRC GDPR Research and Confidentiality and ONS Safe Researcher Training. Both courses cannot, by nature, be TRE-specific but assume that researchers have some knowledge of research methodology, data science, and data protection that is covered elsewhere. Researchers also need an understanding of “anonymisation”, must know something about the data they will be accessing, and are able to obtain information about their specific TRE and the service’s data governance process.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has partnered with the University of Edinburgh’s Data-Driven Innovation Talent team²⁶ to design a training module covering these elements: “Data Access - Working in TREs for non-traditional researchers”. Screenshot extracts of the module can be seen in Appendix 8.7. The learning module and teaching materials are designed to be interactive and engaging. A short assessment is integrated at the end of each teaching unit and quizzing and reflection for the user to self-monitor their learning and demonstrate evidence of learning in data protection and working with sensitive data, with an emphasis on personal responsibility as a safe researcher throughout. On successful completion of the module, a certificate of achievement is generated online, and will act as evidence that robust governance standards have been achieved before granting access to sensitive health and social care data.

²⁴ [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(06\)68497-3/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(06)68497-3/fulltext)

²⁵ <https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf>

²⁶ <https://www.ed.ac.uk/medicine-vet-medicine/postgraduate/postgraduate-blog/meet-the-hsc-ddi-talent-programme-team>

Sign a user access agreement, countersigned by a senior member of their organisation

Alongside the organisational agreement, individual researchers should know their responsibilities, expected behaviours, and any consequences should these not be followed. See contracts section (7.6) for how these agreements may differ from those already in place for traditional researchers.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch have a User Access Agreement that is signed by both our lead data controller and the researcher organisation. This is based on the Scottish National Safe Haven User Agreement²⁷.

6.2.4 National organisations supporting TREs should consider maintaining a national unsafe user and organisation list on behalf of TREs

TREs experience very few incidents of malicious misuse of data, however almost all have policies in place on consequences for a researcher should they do so. Legal sanctions are very much a last resort. The most effective sanction threat is seen as removing access from the TRE for a specified period of time; for the individual researcher, their team, or in the most extreme cases, an entire organisation. This disincentive for bad behaviour is higher for research organisations completing many projects within a TRE, however at present there is no described sanction stopping researchers behaving maliciously in more than one TRE. A nationally maintained list of unsafe users and organisations, with processes for appeals and removal after a period of time where evidence is provided of issue resolution, would be a strong incentive to good behaviour.

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Principle: Access to health data by non-traditional researchers is acceptable if breaches of terms and conditions are proportionately penalised, such as through fines or being prevented from accessing the data in future.

“It’s a great idea in theory. To my understanding the data is held with the data custodians, and when they have a request for data, it’s minimised datasets, so they can remove certain elements. ... But I think they’re being a bit naïve about data protection...Rather than talking about how secure their datasets are, what are the consequences if that data gets out?”

Implementation within the DataLoch service

Following this DARE UK sprint, Research Data Scotland²⁸ is now investigating what is required for a Scotland-wide unsafe user and organisation list to be put in place, however it may be more effective to create a UK-wide version supported by a national research service such as HDR UK.

7.3. Safe Settings

TREs most often provide access to data via a Virtual Desktop Interface (VDI) within a secure, firewalled area that has been assessed as appropriate for the data use. Common statistical analytical software is installed as standard

²⁷ <https://www.isdscotland.org/Products-and-Services/eDRIS/docs/eDRIS-User-Agreement-v16.pdf>

²⁸ <https://researchdata.scot/>

for researchers, which is maintained by the TRE provider and access to the external world (including the internet) is cut off.

As a minimum, TREs should assess their safe settings against the HDR UK guidelines²⁹. For traditional researchers, TREs often support virtual machines (VMs) with standard, risk-assessed, analytical software. To support non-traditional researchers, TRE safe settings will likely need the following things:

6.3.1. TREs should develop services to:

Increase approved software libraries

Traditional researchers have relied on standard statistical software such as SAS, SPSS, R, etc which have been risk-assessed and are able to function within a TRE (i.e., without access to the internet). This risk assessment needs to be extended to the common tools used by non-traditional researchers (e.g., Python) and made available as standard approved libraries. This may also encompass the ability to allow researchers access to a limited set of external repositories (e.g., CRAN, PyPI) for additional software installation. Such access needs to be tightly controlled, for example through the use of mirrors or proxies with specific auditing and user control.

Allow virtual machines with varying configurations of hardware access and temporary internet access

Non-traditional researchers and projects are more likely to require new, open source, bespoke or proprietary software. The installation process is likely to require internet access at some point, which should then be removed, and the TRE space locked down when install is complete.

This solution should also allow for scalable storage and computing power to be available, as more researchers require access to truly big data for AI/ML development³⁰.

Security risk assess new software and allow installation separately to data access

Software requirements will need to be defined by researchers during the project application phase. Any non-standard software should be assessed for security risks via a process agreed with the data provider as early as possible to avoid wasted effort. This assessment should occur before data is transferred into the VM to minimise risks of data breach. If further software updates are required after data access has commenced, this should be done either isolated from the data, or data access should be paused while software is installed.

New software requirements are likely to vary far more than for traditional researchers (although some tools such as Python are common). TREs therefore need to be able to allow bespoke software builds for projects, into a virtual area isolated from other projects to prevent software install that risks all projects.

Support delegated software installation

The increased range of software required to support innovative research and non-traditional researchers requires a corresponding increase in the range of skills and resource required to install and support that software. In many cases, TRE providers are poorly-placed to provide this support, and doing so would incur excessive costs or delays to the project. TRE providers should develop mechanisms to allow researchers (or those working on their behalf)

²⁹ [Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems:](https://zenodo.org/record/5767586#.Yr2Dm3bMKUk)
<https://zenodo.org/record/5767586#.Yr2Dm3bMKUk>

³⁰ Kavianpour et al. A Review of Trusted Research Environments to Support Next Generation Capabilities based on Interview Analysis Preprint: <https://s3.ca-central-1.amazonaws.com/assets.jmir.org/assets/preprints/preprint-33720-accepted.pdf>

to carry out software installation. This can only happen in an environment with no data access (as per 7.3.1.3), and as part of a security process agreed with the data provider.

Isolate non-traditional researcher project spaces/virtual machines

Any access to data by organisations will be agreed with the data provider, and any security risks assessed, and mitigations approved. To minimise the risk, the project or group of projects should be isolated, particularly from spaces containing data from other data providers. This may require changes to audit and testing regimes in TREs to evaluate software security and malware on a project-focused basis, rather than to the entire TRE area and standard software installs.

6.3.2 TRE access should be restricted to organisationally managed machines and organisationally managed IP addresses only

In existing TREs, access to the VDI service is usually limited to IP addresses controlled by researcher organisations. This has multiple benefits; in particular, it minimises the risk of individuals who may leave an organisation, from continuing to access the TRE, and helps the organisation conform to the requirements placed on them. For many such organisations, this pattern of access is normal and so this requirement is trivial to fulfil. For non-traditional organisations this may be less common, but this requirement nevertheless should be retained.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

For a full technical description of the TRE infrastructure used by DataLoch for non-traditional researchers, see the forthcoming paper from University of Edinburgh's Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre (EPCC)³¹. In brief:

DataLoch has a separate TRE space for non-traditional researcher access, following HDR UK guidelines. Within this space, VMs are created for each project with an initial standard software build including CRAN and PyPi libraries as devised by non-traditional researchers and agreed with data providers. The infrastructure and process allows researchers to specify software requirements and build a custom VM. A web proxy can be enabled temporarily by TRE administrators to allow software install by researchers. Any custom build software installation follows a process agreed with data providers and TRE technical staff to review all novel software requests for security risks.

See Appendix 9.1 for a project process flow requiring new software and Appendix 9.2 for the architecture diagram of the TRE infrastructure used by DataLoch – including traditional and non-traditional researcher access.

7.4. Safe Data

Data should be shared as openly as possible to be used to its full potential. However, any personal data use must be minimised to comply with data protection laws – no matter who is using it for what purpose. TREs and governance panels assess whether the data and level of detail within is appropriate for the specific project use in the required setting.

³¹ Scobbie, D (2022) "Trusted Research Environment and Data Safe Haven Design Evolution" expected publication in 2022.

6.4.1. Data providers should document any restrictions or caveats on use or users

It is likely that some data detail is not appropriate to be used for AI or commercial use (for example) due to being commercially or otherwise sensitive. Rather than restricting data access entirely, data providers should be encouraged to assess risks of data detail and add any additional safeguards considered appropriate (e.g., restricting levels of detail of variables, requiring physical TRE access, etc) for different types of organisations. TREs or Information Governance experts may be able to support data providers in this risk assessment. Researchers equally should be made aware that some levels of data detail may not be available to all researchers.

From the public deliberation workshops

“I think saying the term ‘Artificial intelligence’ makes me go, ‘Oh, that’s weird,’ just because it’s so new and it’s like stepping into the unknown in terms of medicine. But there’s so much scope to do so much good...”

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has Data Terms of Use agreements with each data provider, and for providers with multiple datasets agreements are in place for each dataset outlining conditions of use such as restrictions on access for researchers, which are reviewed for project extracts.

6.4.2. TRE and governance review panels should have some training in AI/ML techniques to understand data requirements and contributions to results – this should be supplemented by expertise from the AI sphere where required

TRE staff and governance panels assess whether the amount and detail of data requested is appropriate for the proposed analysis and proportionate to the anticipated public benefit. TRE staff are often versed in statistical techniques, so can provide guidance, or understand at least how data requests and models are appropriate. Building AI/ML models often requires a more exploratory approach – requesting lots of data without being able to specify how each variable will contribute to the model. This goes against the grain for TRE/review staff charged with only providing the minimal data required. Training in AI/ML would support TRE services and review panels on how these techniques may require a different risk assessment approach and follows previous recommendations on providing appropriate training to bridge gaps between health research and software development³². Training in cutting-edge techniques will also support TRE staff career-progression and may improve retention – a nationally recognised issue³³.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has engaged an AI specialist as an ethics panel member and is investigating the most relevant AI training for the wider team and governance review panels.

³² <https://www.oecd.org/els/health-systems/health-data-governance.htm>

³³ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1067053/goldacre-review-using-health-data-for-research-and-analysis.pdf

6.4.3. Disclosure risks for other types of data (e.g. qualitative, image, genomic) – for both working within the TRE and when exporting as output – need to be identified and mitigated by data providers, TREs, and researchers

Most TREs allow access to structured quantitative data, where risks are fairly well known and processes exist to minimise data on preparation before allowing access (following guidance from e.g. ICO) and on research outputs. Some individual TREs and projects (e.g., the Scottish Medical Imaging³⁴ service and PICTURES project³⁵, UCL Clinical Record Interactive Service³⁶) are allowing access to different types of data, but this is generally limited to specific areas (e.g. the SMI project pseudonymises radiology free text reports, where a growing number of Natural Language Processing researchers are interested in wider clinical notes, which have a different risk profile).

As TREs develop to support non-traditional researchers developing AI models requiring different data, a UK-wide effort should be made to publicise the understanding of disclosure risks of different types of data – both during preparation to be used within a TRE, and should they need to be exported from that environment.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch has begun a workstream that will support researcher access to de-identified free-text clinical notes used within health data. This will focus on Natural Language Processing (NLP) based de-identification of various types of clinical reports. This workstream includes public engagement to understand public perception of the use of clinical notes and NLP.

7.5. Safe Outputs

Anything that needs removing from the secure environment is routinely checked by TRE staff for risks that an individual can be identified. In order to best support non-traditional researchers, we recommend:

6.5.1. Risks and mitigations of outputs from novel analysis techniques, tools, software and data need to be identified and understood by TRE staff and researchers. Safe output criteria should be developed between TREs for consistency

Non-traditional researchers using non-standard software for unfamiliar (to TRE staff) analysis techniques means “safe” or “disclosive” is not necessarily defined for all types of output. As described by other TRE reports³⁷, AI models bring new risks of data export, however innocently deployed. The work and recommendations from the DARE UK GRAIMatter sprint should be adopted to support understanding of risks of outputs. Publishing of this knowledge between TREs in a similar manner to the Statistical Disclosure Control handbook³⁸ will give researchers the best experience when working between them.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch eagerly anticipates implementing the recommendations from the GRAIMatter DARE UK sprint when published to support AI/ML model output checks.

³⁴ <https://www.isdscotland.org/Products-and-Services/eDRIS/Scottish-Medical-Imaging-Service/>

³⁵ <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/hic/casestudies/pictures/>

³⁶ <https://www.maudsleybrc.nihr.ac.uk/facilities/clinical-record-interactive-search-cris/cris-natural-language-processing>

³⁷ Kavianpour et al. A Review of Trusted Research Environments to Support Next Generation Capabilities based on Interview Analysis Preprint: <https://s3.ca-central-1.amazonaws.com/assets.jmir.org/assets/preprints/preprint-33720-accepted.pdf>

³⁸ <https://securedatagroup.org/sdc-handbook/>

6.5.2. Any TRE-specific disclosure control policies and requirements should be made clear to researchers during the project application process

TREs have rules- or principles-based safe output policies. Making these available early in the process, including information on what is and isn't acceptable, and when negotiation is possible and appropriate, will provide clarity to researchers about the output process. Principles could be published online or provided to researchers within application packs for example.

Until risks of AI outputs are understood and articulated to TRE staff and researchers, those researchers utilising such techniques should be made aware of the need to work with TRE staff on understanding the risks that might be within their outputs, and how they can support TREs in demonstrating their safety.

Implementation within the DataLoch service

DataLoch provide output principles with the TRE login information – any projects identified as potentially causing output issues (e.g., on rare disease types) are discussed with the researchers during project specification.

6.5.3. TREs should follow up on how project results were used and benefits realised

There is strong support for public benefit (over profit) motivation for projects, with project benefits that are fed back into the health system, as well as a desire for TREs, researchers and national reviewers³⁹ in partnership to do more than the base legal requirements for dissemination of research⁴⁰.

Projects using personal data must have public benefit by law. How that benefit is measured has largely been left to TRE/data provider review panels. Some TREs may fulfil author or contributor criteria⁴¹ for academic work, depending on their level of support of the project, and therefore could have a requirement to be informed about any published papers. However, while traditional researchers are required to publish and disseminate results widely (i.e., funding obligations), non-traditional researchers may disseminate in a less public way, or based on different motivations – e.g. within their own organisation to further product development. Given TREs are central nodes for research networks, TREs should follow up with researchers after the data are accessed to check how the project results are being used, with project summaries published by TREs to include project benefits.

The requirement for engaging with the process should not be onerous to complete and should be made clear to researchers during the application process, alongside the possible consequences of not engaging e.g., removal of access to data. This requirement could be included within the data access agreements signed by researchers.

The follow-up process should continue far beyond the data access point and responses published publicly (including controls put in place) to increase public and data provider trust in data sharing, reduce perceptions of commercial data grabs, and better describe how public benefit can be derived from exploratory and innovative projects.

³⁹ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1067053/goldacre-review-using-health-data-for-research-and-analysis.pdf

⁴⁰ <https://dataloch.org/sites/default/files/2022-07/Public%20deliberations%20on%20access%20to%20health%20data%20by%20non-traditional%20researchers.pdf>

⁴¹ [ICMJE | Recommendations | Defining the Role of Authors and Contributors](#)

From the public deliberation workshops

Key Principle: Researchers are open to having their research and its outputs audited after being granted access to the data.

“It’s an issue of transparency and who’s funding what, and how the research is being used.”

Implementation within the DataLoch service

The DataLoch follow up process checks in with key project team members biannually via a short survey and plans to publish outcomes on the data use register.

7.6. Risk Assessment and Contracts

Alongside the project specific aspects of governance, overarching documentation is in place in TREs to allow them to function legally, fairly and ethically. This is compiled between the TRE and data provider legal teams before allowing non-traditional researcher access.

6.6.1. TRE governance documentation such as risk assessments should be amended to include specifics in relation to non-traditional researcher data access.

TRE Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) or other risks assessment should include information on:

- a) any new types of researcher accessing data (e.g. commercial organisations); and
- b) technological changes made to accommodate this (e.g. requirement to have some internet access for software installation).

Organisational & Individual Researcher Data Access Agreements should include clauses on:

- a) Sanctions for misuse – including potentially banning researchers or organisations from TREs;
- b) Intellectual Property Rights and responsibilities regarding both the data provided by and to the researcher and outputs from research;
- c) Agreement for the research organisation providing software that this has no known security weaknesses, harmful software code, is appropriately up to date and has valid licences where appropriate; and
- d) Any publication or follow-up requirements for researchers.

Data Sharing/Data Processing Agreements between data providers and TRE providers (if separate) should include clauses on:

- a) Information on what data (and detail levels) can and cannot be used for by different researchers, and under what circumstances for each dataset; and
- b) Any Intellectual Property Rights responsibilities for, for example, any models or tools developed using the data. This should be reflected in organisational agreements above.

TRE and Data Provider Data Privacy Notices should be checked and amended to include all types of researchers/organisations accessing the data

Implementation within the DataLoch service

The DataLoch contractual agreements relating to these relationships are summarised below:

8. Conclusion and Further Work

As further researchers apply to use the service, TREs will continue to develop to support novel data use in line with the safeguards expected by the public regarding personal and sensitive data. This document has described recommended amendments to current governance for TREs to support the safe health data use for AI and software developers and researchers from beyond academia or clinical settings. These recommendations have been implemented in one Scottish TRE (DataLoch) and are currently being piloted with researchers.

Some recommendations within this report relate to data governance or ethics panels. Some TREs may not have control or influence over these processes and so feel this is outside the scope of TRE activity. Here we would argue for national bodies such as HDR UK, HRA and UKRI to support TREs in continuing to encourage the changes required for emerging technologies to be used safely.

It is expected that some of the recommendations may not be applicable across all TRE setups and we welcome feedback or national guidance on how they can be adapted across TREs.

8.1. Limitations and Further Work

This Sprint project revealed multiple opportunities for further guidance and development of TREs. Some of the issues identified include:

Extending scope:

- These recommendations are designed for use within UK-based TREs allowing remote access by UK researchers only as part of this DARE UK Sprint. There is obviously benefit in extending beyond in further work such as data provision to worldwide resources, or data use for other purposes (e.g. service management).
- Restrictions in some TREs mean only pseudonymised data can be held – requiring workaround for some uses of data (e.g. Natural Language Processing of qualitative data). Developing processes to allow safe use of de-identified qualitative or other newer data types would expand the utility of data further.
- Data providers will also have to consider whether to provide access to non-traditional research users data outside of TRE environments. An IT Security Assessment can support use of data in many environments, but when providing data outside of the TRE, the assessment can only rely on what is provided by the organisation – some of whom may not have the required security or documentation to handle such sensitive data.

AI expertise and understanding

- Experts in the areas required to support this governance model – e.g. in AI data ethics/advanced disclosure control – are rare. There is a need to recruit or upskill resource in this area across TREs and their ethics panels and data access gatekeepers. It is possible that this expertise lies with non-traditional researchers themselves.
- Understanding of the risks of AI/Machine Learning outputs from TREs, and the processes required to make these outputs safe are currently in their infancy – recommendations from the GRAIMatter DARE UK Sprint endorsed by DARE UK/HDR UK are welcomed.

Technical Development/TRE specific requirements

Some technical areas were not fully explored with further work required to refine recommendations and guidance for TREs on the following areas:

- Proprietary software with little or no security documentation – how to risk assess, what if it has intellectual property rights, what if it can't be installed into TRE for any reason?
- Some software may require internet access to run, this can be restricted within the TRE to specific sites, but will need data provider input and security risks assessed for TREs.
- Traditional research organisations usually have VPNs which are a limited list of IP addresses – however smaller start-ups etc may not have fixed IP addresses.

Public Engagement development

We recommend further exploration of public perspectives around:

- The public value and specific ethical considerations of AI and machine learning innovators;
- Perspectives on differing trust levels for national and international research and innovation;
- The perceived contradiction between profit and social value;
- The influence of track records of both researchers and organisations in building or reducing perceived levels of trustworthiness.

Non-traditional researcher TRE credibility

We recommend expansion of the training workstream to:

- Pursue national accreditation and training alignment project, through engagement with relevant stakeholders and partners (e.g. SAIL, ONS, eDRIS) to align training delivery, standards, and achieve formal accreditation for the non-traditional researcher training module.
- Establish a national non-traditional researcher education working group and advisory service for the community of learners to share best practice and support.
- Establish a non-traditional researcher education community hub sharing regular information and updates on governance and data access requirements and a series of online webinars and networking events.

9. Appendices

9.1. Glossary

Word/Acronym	Definition
Aggregate data	summary data which is acquired by combining individual-level data and maybe collected from multiple sources and/or on multiple measures, variables, or individuals.
AI data ethics	a set of guidelines that advise on the design and outcomes of the use of data and artificial intelligence, considering such factors as harm to rights and freedoms of individuals, fairness and equality and data bias – these principles support AI developers and data users to consider consequences in AI applications and use of data, particularly due to poor upfront research design and biased datasets: https://www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/ai-ethics
AI models/techniques	the use of digital technology to create systems capable of performing tasks commonly thought to require intelligence - generally involving machines finding patterns in large amounts of data. Here this includes Machine Learning/Deep Learning/Natural Linguistic Processing and many other techniques – see a Glossary of AI for further information: https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.357.6346.19
Data Provider	an organisation that provides data for use by researchers within a TRE. This may be the data controller, or an organisation nominated to act on their behalf.
Ethical Review	a process where a defined project is scrutinised by a party external to the project team to identify and mitigate ethical risks, including ethical risks of the project not being completed.
Ethics Panel	the group/individual who assesses the ethical application and provides opinion or approval on the ethics of the project. Such committees include local research ethics committees (LRECs) based in specific universities and research centres, multicentre research ethics committees (MRECs) and national panels such as NSDEC.
Governance Review Panel	the group/individual who assesses the data governance application based on proportionality and public benefit and approves access or requests changes. Panels often include the Data Controllers responsible for approving the use of their data for the project. In some instances, this could just be a single responsible individual who approves the application e.g. Caldicott guardian in the case of health data. In other instances, the panel may have other representatives such as members of the public.
Individual or row level data	a data set whose columns are different types of measurements/images/features, and where each row contains the record of an individual person or organisation. It is synonymous with ‘record-level data’ or ‘microdata’, and in contrast to aggregated data.
Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	patents, rights to inventions, copyright and related rights, moral rights, trade marks, business names and domain names, rights in get-up, goodwill and the right to sue for passing off or unfair competition, rights in designs, rights in computer software, database rights, rights to use, and protect the confidentiality of, confidential information (including know-how and trade secrets) and all other intellectual property rights, in each case whether registered or unregistered and including all applications and rights to apply for and be granted, renewals or extensions of, and rights to claim priority from, such rights and all similar or equivalent rights or forms of protection which subsist or will subsist now or in the future in any part of the world;

Internet Protocol Address (IP address)	a unique address with a numerical label such as <i>192.0.2.1</i> that computing devices use to identify themselves and communicate with other devices in the IP network. Any device connected to the IP network must have a unique IP address within the network. An IP address serves two main functions: network identification and location addressing. Network administrators assign an IP address to each device connected to a network. Such assignments may be on a static (fixed or permanent) or dynamic basis, depending on network practices and software features.
National Statisticians Data Ethics Advisory Committee (NSDEC)	National Statisticians Data Ethics Advisory Committee
Natural Language Processing (NLP)	a subfield of linguistics, computer science, and AI concerned with how to programme a computer to understand and analyse human language as it is spoken and written (natural language). The technology can then extract information and insights contained in documents written in natural language.
Non-traditional Researcher	a researcher not from academic or NHS settings doing quantitative, statistical research, OR any researchers from any setting developing AI or other emerging technology models.
Outputs	all information requested to be released from the TRE - whether code, statistical results, models or tools during and after a Project.
Personal data	any information relating to an identified or identifiable living individual' as per section 3 of the UK Data Protection Act 2018 (which implements the EU's General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR). Personal data is broadly interpreted, especially via the concept of 'identifiable' which is further defined as 'a living individual who can be identified, directly or indirectly in particular by reference to (a)an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data or an online identifier, or (b)one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of the individual'.
Personal Data	as defined in the Data Protection Legislation.
Project	a defined piece of work looking to answer a question, develop a tool or further knowledge in relation to benefiting public health.
Project Application	an application form sent to a TRE Governance Review Panel which explains how the data will be used for the research project. Details of the benefits of the project, technical specifications and security measures to reduce risks are articulated for review.
Research	under UK Policy for Health and Social Care - "research is defined as the attempt to derive generalisable or transferable new knowledge to answer or refine relevant questions with scientifically sound methods" – while this policy only refers to the use of health and social care data – we recommend it covers all personal data use.
Researcher	someone who applies to access personal data within a TRE for a specified project.
Special category personal data	the term used in current UK and EU data protection legislation for personal data. The special categories are race; ethnic origin; political opinions; religious or philosophical beliefs; trade union membership; genetic data; biometric data (where this is used for identification purposes); health data; data about sex life; and sexual orientation. There are additional legal requirements which must be met to process special category personal data.
Sponsor	the individual, organisation or partnership that takes on overall responsibility for proportionate, effective arrangements being in place to set up, run and report a research project. All health and social care research has a sponsor.

Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC)	methods used to statistically remove, hide or obfuscate results to reduce the risks of identifiable data being included.
Traditional Researcher	researchers from academic organisations or NHS clinicians doing quantitative, statistical research using standard statistical software.
Trusted Research Environment (TRE)	a service providing a secure analytical environment where the data users have substantial freedom to work with detailed row-level data but are prevented from importing or releasing data without permission, and typically are subject to a monitoring and a significant degree of access control – also known as ‘research data centre’, ‘secure data environment’, or ‘safe haven’.
User Access Agreement	an agreement signed by each researcher for each project outlining that they agree to the terms and conditions of use of the TRE and data, and understand the behaviour expected of them and the sanctions should they breach these conditions. Signed by both the researcher and on behalf of their organisation.
Virtual Machine (VM)	a compute resource that uses software instead of a physical computer to run programs and deploy apps. One or more virtual “guest” machines run on a physical “host” machine or server. Each VM runs its own operating system and functions separately from the other VMs, even when they are all running on the same host. This means that, for example, a virtual MacOS virtual machine can run on a physical PC.

9.2. DataLoch Project Process diagram (novel software)

9.3. DataLoch TRE Architecture Diagram

9.4. DataLoch Organisational Criteria

Purpose

This document is intended for to describe the considerations made when an organisation (third- or private-sector) applies for DataLoch hosted data access or consultancy services. The criteria helps assess how well the organisation fits with DataLoch’s purpose, and identify potential risks and control mechanisms.

Date of Completion: <i>(information correct based on what is known at this date)</i>	
What is the ask of DataLoch: <i>(high-level statement on service/activity and purpose – e.g., commissioned analyses for pharma research)</i>	
Organisation Role: <i>(e.g., health technology developer, pharmaceutical)</i>	
Organisation name:	
Relevant Names and Roles: <i>List all those contacted in relation to DL activity – check EOI summary/conversation tracker</i>	

Criteria	Considerations/Principles	Outcome/Notes
Due Diligence:		
Organisational experience	<p>Can the organisation show examples of successful completion of similar projects/collaborations involving personal or sensitive data access? May be in relation to healthcare data, finance, insurance or consumer gathered data.</p> <p>[Likely sources – news sections of websites, known partnerships with other organisations, search engine results – list links used]</p>	
Company values	<p>Consider whether values align to NHS and DataLoch values and priorities</p> <p>[Likely sources – values section of website, organisation LinkedIn profile, company registries, search for “org name” + “breach” or “ico” for information about data breaches] – list sources here with information. Also consider any evidence of living of values.</p>	
Regional Benefit	Note if the organisation has interests in the SE Scotland region, especially those that offer sustained value to the region.	
Financial Assessment Outcome	Due diligence assessment into historical and projected financial position, using standard tools e.g. Dunn & Bradstreet financial reporting tool.	
Location of organisation HQ	Note address. If HQ is not in the UK, there may be UK GDPR risks to consider.	

Contractual arrangements		
Nature of relationship with DataLoch	<i>(can be more than one)</i> Two-way data sharing Commissioned analyses Part of collaboration community Knowledge sharing Product development & innovation Access to market Transactional or Strategic (if strategic, complete section below)	
Nature of organisation	e.g. Small Medium Enterprise (SME) Large commercial 3 rd Sector Charity Other Note any information of note – e.g., University spin off	
Nature of the contract	Organisational framework agreement with standard core responsibilities/data owners, IPR considerations etc. or Part of a wider or more strategic partnership agreement	
Intellectual Property (IP) arrangements	Note any IPR arrangements not covered by standard clauses in organisational framework agreement, if known - e.g. specific arrangements around benefit sharing.	
Questions to be answered	Note any questions relating to how DataLoch and this organisation might work together.	

Some partnerships with DataLoch may be more strategic, with long-term value from an ongoing collaboration for DataLoch and the NHS. If so, DataLoch would expect a strong strategic alignment using the criteria below.

Strategic Partnership Considerations		
Partnership value	Value for NHS for patients, clinicians, and efficiency. <i>(e.g., Product access, clinical workflow improvements, direct patient care, indirect patient impacts, data improvement.</i> <i>Potential unintended negative impact for patients or clinicians.)</i>	
	Financial/knowledge sharing/data value for NHS/DataLoch. <i>(e.g., Product benefit share, potential royalties, DataLoch cost recovery and investment.)</i>	
Innovation	Willingness to engage in collaborative innovation.	
	Novelty in innovation area	

Strategic alignment	Strength of business model and market understanding. <i>(e.g., Alignment to NHS and DDI strategic priorities. Opportunities for integration with NHS systems, include consideration of long-term business model)</i>	
	Ambition <i>(e.g., Ability to scale, if not scaled yet.)</i>	
Cultural alignment	Willingness to share expertise <i>(e.g., Usher Innovation membership, application development, regulation, database management, networks.)</i>	
	Transparency/honesty <i>(e.g., Transparency of business models and motivations.)</i>	

9.5. DataLoch relevant questions in Application Process

Recommendation : Describe public, organisation and health service benefit of research

Background and Public Benefit Statement (max 200 words)

Please include reflections on the following:

- Why is the project is needed and what benefits will there be for patients and/or the wider public?
- What is the overall number of people and/or proportion of a specific affected population that could benefit from the research? (E.g., number of people with a particular condition in the UK)
- How are end-users and/or service providers already involved in defining the project and therefore providing an understanding of potential benefits?
- What are the potential benefits for the NHS – either direct or indirect (including financial if applicable) – that could result from the project?

Are any commercial organisations involved in this project or in the outcome of this work?	Yes: <input type="checkbox"/> No: <input type="checkbox"/>
If yes, please provide details of the commercial organisation(s) role in the project below (if more than one organisation is involved please provide details of each organisation).	
Organisation name	Details of involvement
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Recommendation : Software assessment

If accessing data via the Private Project Zone, identify the software stack and technical specifications.

Software Stack*

Including software programme (e.g. Python, R), software package (e.g. Numpy, Pandas), and custom scripts (e.g. in-house developed code not available in a public repository)

*Note: **no** GCC languages will be permitted on the Private Project Zone virtual machines

Software Programme / Package	Necessary?	Justification	Nature of Software
Tools/Software			
e.g. MedCAT	Yes	NLP tool for analysis	Open source
Libraries/Packages and Installations			
e.g. python3	Yes	Main processing language	Open Source
e.g. CAT	Yes	Necessary library/package	Open Source

Technical Specifications

	Operating System	Linux (Ubuntu 20.04) [non-flexible]
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Technical Specs	Build Arena for installing software/packages	In the build arena, 30GB of software space is provided for software installation and minor testing. Does this meet your requirements? (If not, specify requirements and reasoning) Click or tap here to enter text.
	PPZ Virtual Machine	The standard build is 32GB RAM, 4 cores, with 10GB of storage. Does this meet your requirements? (If not, specify requirements and reasoning) Click or tap here to enter text.
Retention Details	Retention Duration (how long do you need access to the platform)	
	Retention Content (what do you need access to the platform for the duration answered above)	

Recommendation : Sponsorship

Do you have sponsorship for your project? Information about ACCORD sponsorship: https://www.accord.scot/research-access/sponsorship	Yes: <input type="checkbox"/> No: <input type="checkbox"/> Under Review: <input type="checkbox"/>
If yes or under review please confirm sponsorship reference number and organisation:	

Recommendations 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 : Researcher experience and training

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List below all those who need access to the data Note: All individuals requiring access to the data are required to have completed training within the last 2 years and this should be renewed within 2 years of completing that training. The course you are advised to complete is the free MRC Online Training 'Research, GDPR and confidentiality e-learning' which you can access here. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> You must complete the 10 modules in Research, GDPR and confidentiality - what you really need to know and provide a screenshot of completion. Then complete the Quiz and provide a copy of the certificate. Please refer to the eDRIS website (https://www.isdscotland.org/Products-and-services/Edris/FAQ-eDRIS/#c1) or discuss with the DataLoch team on other accepted forms of training. 				
Title & Full Name	Job Title and Organisation	Email	Access required	Please give details of the relevant expertise of the applicant(s)/research team and how it applies to the field(s) to be researched:

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Recommendation : Follow up

Please describe all routes by which outputs or results will be shared, and with which groups/audiences [including the wider public]

Please note, when sharing, the confidentiality of this information must be maintained. For additional guidance and support liaise with the DataLoch team who can support.

9.6. DataLoch Follow up process

Purpose

DL projects are followed up to ascertain if and how

- results of projects are used
- benefits of the project have been realised, and
- if not – discuss ways forward to hold the organisation accountable to the signed agreements
- either way – follow up results are published to maintain public transparency.

Findings and results of projects do not need to be published academic work, acceptable methods include open or paid access journals (as per ICO guidelines), presentation at conferences/meetings, white papers, reports returned to data providing organisations, product development and testing within NHS/other organisations, supporting discussions with stakeholders, etc.

Benefits of this process:

- Supports responsible use of data – more tangible support for public benefit and value of research – especially from non-traditional researchers (i.e., those that make profit too)
- Increased robustness of DataLoch process.
- Supports researchers by aligning with FAIR research principles and wider dissemination of work
- Increased trust (by within system and public) in non-traditional organisations (i.e., ones without established, defined research purpose/short term organisations) using data.
- Supports ICO guidance on using data for research (draft) requirements of publication of results, and commitment to sharing findings of research

Limitations

It is acknowledged that researchers are likely to be focused on disseminating their results rather than providing updates to DL, therefore this process is required to be as straightforward as possible to encourage engagement from researchers, but provide feedback to the public of project value.

Impact of projects is likely to take many months/years to accomplish, therefore the DL process allows a flexible timeframe to report back.

Scope:

All DataLoch projects with a DataLoch application form (including delivered by CIT, service management, research, innovation)

INSTRUCTIONS/PROCEDURE

Application

Researchers complete consideration of:

- a) Why is the project needed and what benefits will there be for patients and/or the wider public?

- b) What is the overall number of people and/or proportion of a specific affected population that could benefit from the research? (E.g., number of people with a particular condition in the UK)
- c) How are end-users and/or service providers already involved in defining the project?
- d) How would the outcomes and outputs of the project impact frontline services?
- e) What are the potential benefits for the NHS – either direct or indirect (including financial if applicable) – that could result from the project?

Post Data Delivery

1 month after delivery:

Service Manager contacts Lead Researcher and Professional Service Lead via email asking for feedback including:

- Does the data released meet what is required for the project? (Yes/No)
- What is the estimated timeline for dissemination? (within 6 months, longer)

6 months after delivery (and every 6 months until 6 months after project end date (unless indicated otherwise by Lead Researcher/Professional Service Lead):

Service Manager contacts Lead Researcher and Professional Service Lead via email to:

- Confirm number of output requests received/processed so far (counted from Output Tracker)
- Reiterate project aim, public benefit statement and dissemination plan from application form and ask for report on progress – template report can be provided if required.
- Reiterate obligations signed in organisational agreement of publishing results and letting DataLoch know.
- Confirm that any published reports or progress will be published on DataLoch website to promote public benefit gained from the research, along with offer to promote via a news item or via DL networks.
- Confirm a lack of results is still worth disseminating.
- Confirm DL will be back in touch in 6 months unless we hear otherwise to check on progress.

This contact may be in form of a feedback survey confirming projects outputs have been used for e.g.:

- Submitting to be published/published in academic journals
- Conferences/presentations
- Discussions with policy makers/stakeholders
- Testing in Industry
- Decision not to progress
- Developing new project proposals
- Any other developments (free text)

Responses are documented by Service Manager on Data Use Register under output information field and Projects Delivered Webpages – with e.g. links to publications, notes on dissemination progress.

If no response within 1 month, Lead Researcher/Professional Service Lead and signatory to User Agreements informed data access may be revoked/future access denied without engagement and this response will be published.

If no response within 2 months, confirm with Lead Researcher/Professional Service Lead that data access revoked/future data access may not occur and data will be archived/data must be deleted. Service Manager (or delegate) updates Data Use Register/Projects Delivered webpage to confirm action taken.

9.7. Training module

Screenshot extracts of training module: “Data Access - Working in TREs for non-traditional researchers”

Course Overview

This course includes an introduction and 6 core modules:

- Module 1: Safe People** - being a trusted researcher
- Module 2: Safe Projects** - public benefit and statistical purpose
- Module 3: Safe Settings** - awareness and use of safe settings and data security
- Module 4: Safe Data** - good practice in analytics
- Module 5: Safe Outputs** - disclosure control
- Module 6: Public Engagement & Involvement** - trust and transparency

Data Access and Working in Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

Dashboard / My courses / Data Access and Working in Trusted Research Environments (TREs)

Twitter Feed:

Tweets from @HDR_UK

HDRUK Health Data Research U... @HDR_UK · 1h
The @DARE_UK1 programme, led in partnership with HDR UK and @ADR_UK, has today published recommendations for the design & delivery of a coordinated & trustworthy national #data #research infrastructure.
Find out more bit.ly/3RHLPED

DARE UK @DARE_UK1 · 2h
Today, we have published a set of recommendations for a coordinated & trustworthy national #data #research infrastructure. They're the culmination

Statistical disclosure control and outputs

- Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) is often used to produce 'safer' versions of datasets.
- However when working with potentially identifiable data it needs to be applied to results.
- Why do you think it is important to preserve confidentiality?

We'll look at this in more detail when we cover Safe Outputs.

Can you think of any more?

- Legal penalties
- Reputational risk
- Loss of confidence in data collection
- Fewer observations
- Public trust